

DAMAGES IN QUASI-ISOTROPIC CARBON / EPOXY COMPOSITE LAMINATES WITH CIRCULAR HOLES UNDER MONOTONIC UNIAXIAL LOADING

Jiayu XIAO and Claude BATHIAS

ITMA, Department of Industrial Materials, CNAM, 2, Rue Conté, 75003, Paris, France

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a discussion on the origins of the point strength model and the minimal strength model proposed by Tan and an explanation on the physical signification of the characteristic dimensions adopted by Tan. The results show that two Tan's models are based on an assumption of the stress fields around the hole, the characteristic dimension is the distance between the hole border and the so-called characteristic point at which the ratio of the notched first ply failure (FPF) strength to the ultimate strength may be considered as a material constant. The damage processes of two non woven quasi-isotropic T300/Epoxy laminates with circular holes under monotonic uniaxial loading were investigated. As the first damage, the cracks in the 90° plies detected by acoustic emission and verified by radiography were found to be one of the main damage features. As influencing the delamination adjacent to the free-edges, the stacking sequences also influence the crack propagation. The ratio of the notched FPF strength measured at the hole border to the ultimate strength, only treated as a quasi-constant, is logically inferior to the material constant predicted by the models. The ultimate notched strengths predicted are in good agreement with the experimental results.

Keywords: Composite, Laminate, Damage, Notched strength, Carbon fiber, Epoxy

INTRODUCTION

The point and average stress criteria [1] consider only the local or average stress at a point adjacent to the hole along the ligament. The two criteria can give good results to predict the notched strengths. Although the stress concentration coefficient in these criteria can be recalculated as rigidity degrades, the lamination theory can not be easily applied to the notched laminates. The two parameter criterion proposed in [2] develops the point stress criterion in [1]. Although the precision can be modified, the lamination theory can not also be applied to the notched laminates easily. The point strength model and minimal strength model were proposed and used by Tan in [3-6]. The models not only can predict the notched laminate strengths with a good precision, but also can partially explain the damage mechanism [7-8] due to the application of laminate damage criteria.

However, the characteristic dimensions, as empirical parameters, often adopted in these criteria have no clear physical signification. In addition, the damage processes of composite laminates with holes under monotonic uniaxial loading need further investigation both by experiments and by models. This paper attempts to explain the origins of the point strength model and the minimal strength model which are proposed by Tan, to explain the physical signification of characteristic dimensions adopted in them and then to predict the notched laminate strength.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTS

Two T300/Epoxy 914 laminates, fabricated by Aérospatiale in France, were tested and studied. The

laminate stacking sequences and thickness are shown in Table 1. The volumetric fiber fraction is 60%. The essential properties of the unidirectional plates are given in [9].

All specimens are 250 mm in length including 75 mm of end tap. Two ends of each specimen are adhered with a balance E-glass fabric epoxy plate of 1 mm in thickness and 75 mm in length. For notched specimens, a circular hole is drilled to the center, the ratio of the width to the hole diameter is equal to 5, and four hole diameters (3, 5, 8, and 10 mm) are chosen. The unnotched specimen width is 30 mm.

Table 1 Stacking sequences and thickness of the composite laminates

TYPE	DESCRIPTION	STACKING SEQUENCES	THICKNESS
T300/914-1	Carbon/Epoxy 914	[0/0/+45/+45/-45/-45/90/90]s	2.0 mm
T300/914-2	Carbon/Epoxy 914	[0/90/+45/-45/+45/-45/90/0]s	2.0 mm

All specimens are tested with a MAYES machine (25 tons) with a crosshead rate of 0.4 mm/min at room temperature. Five gages are adhered at the ligament (the first is near the hole border and the fifth is near the straight border) to measure the strain distributions and relevant data were acquired with a system piloted with PC-IBM. Acoustic emission (AE) and radiography are adopted to detect and to verify the first damages and the corresponding stresses. After a specimen is loaded to a value that damage was detected by AE, it is unloaded, penetrated by an opaque penetrant (iodide zinc) and then radiographed.

DAMAGE MODELS

By means of the expressions for the point and average stress criteria, two assumptions can be given to explain the origins of the point strength model and the minimal strength model proposed by Tan.

1) Suppose that the stress contribution adjacent to a hole along the ligament in an infinite notched laminate can be expressed by the following equation (see Fig.1a):

Fig.1 Damage models: (a) Point strength model; (b) Minimal strength model

$$\sigma_{yy}(x,0) = \sigma_y^{\infty} \frac{\sigma_{FPF}}{\sigma(x,0)_{FPF, N}} \quad (1)$$

where, $\sigma_{yy}(x,0)$ is the stress contribution along the ligament in an infinite notched laminate;
 $\sigma_x^{\infty}, \sigma_y^{\infty}, \sigma_{xy}^{\infty}$ are the stresses applied to the notched laminate ($\sigma_x^{\infty} = \sigma_{xy}^{\infty} = 0$);
 σ_{FPF} is the unnotched FPF strength of the laminate;
 $\sigma(x,0)_{FPF, N}$ is the notched FPF strength at the point $(x,0)$ in the laminate.

Suppose also that when $\sigma_{yy}(a+b_1,0)$, the stress at the point $(a+b_1,0)$ along the ligament of the

notched laminate, is equal to the unnotched strength of laminate σ_0 , the final fracture of the notched laminate will occur (i.e., σ_y^∞ , the stress applied to the infinite notched laminate, will be equal to the notched strength σ_N^∞). That can be expressed as follows:

$$\text{When } \sigma_{yy}(x,0) \Big|_{x=a+b_1} = \sigma_{yy}(a+b_1,0) = \sigma_0, \quad (1a)$$

where, a and b_1 are semi-major axis and characteristic dimension respectively.

one can obtain:

$$\sigma_y^\infty = \sigma_N^\infty \quad (1b)$$

Finally, one can express the first model, the point strength model, by the following equation:

$$\frac{\sigma(a+b_1,0)_{FPF,N}}{\sigma_N^\infty} = \frac{\sigma_{FPF}}{\sigma_0} = \text{material constant} \quad (1c)$$

2) Suppose that the stress distribution around a hole in an infinite notched laminate can be expressed by the following equation (see Fig.1b):

$$\sigma_{yy}(x,y) = \sigma_y^\infty \frac{\sigma_{FPF}}{\sigma(x,y)_{FPF,N \min}} \quad (2)$$

where, $\sigma_{yy}(x,y)$ is the stress contribution around a hole in an infinite notched laminate;
 $\sigma_x^\infty, \sigma_y^\infty, \sigma_{xy}^\infty$ are the stresses applied to the notched laminate ($\sigma_x^\infty = \sigma_{xy}^\infty = 0$);
 σ_{FPF} is the unnotched FPF strength of the laminate;
 $\sigma(x,y)_{FPF, N \min}$ is the minimal notched FPF strength at point (x,y) around the hole in the laminate.

Suppose also that when $\sigma_{yy}(a+b_0, b+b_0)$, the stress along a curve ‘‘C’’, is equal to the unnotched laminate strength σ_0 , the final fracture of the notched laminate will occur (i.e., σ_y^∞ , the stress applied to the infinite notched laminate, will be equal to the notched strength σ_N^∞). That can be expressed as follows:

$$\text{When } \sigma_{yy}(x,y) \Big|_{x=a+b_0,y=b+b_0} = \sigma_{yy}(a+b_0, b+b_0) = \sigma_0, \quad (2a)$$

where: a , b and b_0 are semi-major axis, semi-minor axis and characteristic dimension respectively.

one can obtain:

$$\sigma_y^\infty = \sigma_N^\infty \quad (2b)$$

Finally, one can obtain the second damage model, the minimal strength model, as follows:

$$\frac{\sigma(a+b_0,b+b_0)_{FPF, N \min}}{\sigma_N^\infty} = \frac{\sigma_{FPF}}{\sigma_0} = \text{material constant} \quad (2c)$$

the curve ‘‘C’’, called as characteristic curve, can be expressed by:

$$\frac{x}{a+b_0} + \frac{y}{b+b_0} = 1 \quad (2d)$$

In equations (1c) and (2c), the stress fields around the hole can be approximately expressed by the analytical solution [10]. The finite width influence on the stress distributions can be considered by the isotropic finite width correction factor [3-6]. In [9], in order to increase the prediction precision, the models were improved by using a numerical solution for the stress field around the hole in a finite width notched specimen and by determining the characteristic dimensions of each ply which are different from one ply to another. The unnotched and notched FPF strengths and the ultimate strengths are determined with the Tsai-Wu quadratic tensor polynomial criterion. In the present paper, relevant calculation was carried out with the VAX, the predicted results presented by equations (1c) and (2c) will be compared with the experimental results and several discussions will be given.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

On the damage models

It should be noted that the two models with the forms expressed in equations (1c) and (2c) can be respectively transformed into equations (3) (3a) and (4) (4a) with a simple arithmetic operation:

$$SRF = \frac{\sigma_N^\infty}{\sigma_0} = \frac{\text{FPF notched strength at } (d_1, 0)}{\text{FPF unnotched strength}} = \frac{\sigma(a+b_1, 0)_{FPF, N}}{\sigma_{FPF}} \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_N^\infty = \frac{\sigma_0}{\sigma_{FPF}} \sigma(a+b_1, 0)_{FPF, N} \quad (3a)$$

$$SRF = \frac{\sigma_N^\infty}{\sigma_0} = \frac{\text{Minimum FPF notched strength at } c}{\text{FPF unnotched strength}} = \frac{\sigma(a+b_0, b+b_0)_{FPF, N \min}}{\sigma_{FPF}} \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_N^\infty = \frac{\sigma_0}{\sigma_{FPF}} \sigma(a+b_0, b+b_0)_{FPF, N \min} \quad (4a)$$

Equations (3) and (4) are respectively the point strength and minimal strength models proposed by Tan. Therefore, it may be considered that the assumptions on stress distributions adjacent to the hole expressed in equations (1) and (2) are the provenances of two Tan's models respectively. Although equations (1) and (2) have not yet been mathematically proven, the models based on them have been practically applied to predict the laminate notched strengths with a good precision. However, it is still expected that equations (1) and (2), as the approximate stress distributions around the hole in the point and the average stress criteria in [1], can be respectively mathematically demonstrated. The proving process will be associated with damage criteria because the FPF strengths need to be determined. Equations (3a) and (4a) permit to determine b_1 and b_0 at a diameter given, then to calculate the notched strengths at different diameters with them.

It should be also noted that in the two models with the forms shown in equations (1c) and (2c), the physical signification of the characteristic dimensions is clear. It can be considered that:

1) There exists always a point adjacent to the hole along the ligament in notched laminates, the ratio of the notched FPF stress at this point to the notched ultimate strength can be equal to the ratio of the unnotched FPF strength to the unnotched ultimate strength, and equal also to a material constant. This point is called as the characteristic point, and the distance between this point and the hole border is the characteristic dimension; or

2) There exists always a point at a curve around the hole in notched laminates, the ratio of the minimal notched FPF strength at this point to the notched ultimate strength can be equal to the ratio of the unnotched FPF strength to the unnotched ultimate strength, and equal also to a material constant. This curve is called as the characteristic curve, and the distance between this curve and the hole border is

the characteristic dimension.

On the damage mechanisms

The damage processes are studied by AE and radiography. The AE rate as a function of the load applied, and the strain at the ligament given by the fifth gage (near the straight free-edge), are recorded, as shown in Fig.2. The notched FPF stresses can be obtained from this figure. But any evident knees due to damages at the load-strain curves can not be observed. However, as shown in [9], evident non-linearity due to damages can be observed from the curve of the load applied vs the strain given by the first gage (near the hole border). This shows that the damage appearance is localized in notched laminates.

Fig.2 Notched first ply failure measured with AE techniques ($\phi=8\text{mm}$): (a) T300/914-1; (b) T300/914-2

Fig.3 Radiography photos at diverse loading levels: (a) T300/914-1 ($\phi=5\text{mm}$); (b) T300/914-2 ($\phi=8\text{mm}$)

Radiography permits to objectively verify the AE measurement results and to know well diverse damages inside laminates. Some representative radiography results are shown in Fig.3.

For T300/914-1, damages undergo several principal stages as follows: 1) Cracks in the 90° plies, as the first intrinsic material damages, are initialized at the hole border. The corresponding load is almost 40%-55% of the ultimate values; 2) The cracks in the 90° plies are multiplied to the specimen length direction and equally evolve towards to the straight free-edges. Contaminated by the damages in the 90° plies, the ±45° plies are cracked both from the hole border and from the cracks in the 90° plies. In addition, cracks appear also in the 0° plies near the hole border; especially, delamination occurs around the hole and adjacent to the straight free-edges; 3) The final fracture in each ply occurs in different angles around the hole. The fracture in the 0° plies is influenced by that in the 90° plies. For T300/914-2, the first damage is also presented in the form of cracks in the 90° plies excited from the hole border. But they are not evident and numerous. Before the final fracture, it is difficult to observe damages in other plies and any delamination does not occur near to the free-edges. The fracture surface is a little smooth. This means that the stacking sequences influence not only the delamination adjacent to the free-edges but also the crack evolution in plies, as pointed in [11].

On the notched FPF and ultimate strength

The experimental results of stresses at the first damage (P₁) and the final fracture (P_u) are shown in Table 2 in which φ is the hole diameter. Each of these values was averaged over five experimental data. The dispersion of the notched ultimate strength is smaller (the maximal relative error is 12%) than that of the notched FPF strength (the maximal relative error is 15%), especially for T300/914-2.

Table 2 Experimental results for the FPF and ultimate strengths

TYPE	φ (mm)	P ₁ (MPa)	P _u (MPa)	P ₁ /P _u (%)
T300/914-1	0.0	317.0	493.5	64.3
	1.5	207.7	410.9	49.7
	2.5	168.0	360.0	47.5
	4.0	137.5	343.2	40.2
	5.0	159.0	340.9	46.0
T300/914-2	0.0	327.1	586.2	55.8
	1.5	206.2	400.4	51.5
	2.5	193.6	360.5	53.7
	4.0	157.5	290.5	54.2
	5.0	136.0	275.6	49.3

Fig.4 Ratio of the FPF strength to the ultimate strengths at different hole size for the laminates tested

Fig.5 Stresses calculated and measured at the first damage and the final fracture (a): For T300/914-1 (b): For T300/914-2

The ratio of the notched FPF strengths to the ultimate strengths, predicted, measured and then verified, is shown in Fig.4. The notched FPF and the ultimate strengths predicted are shown in Figs.5a and 5b.

It is not easy to measure the FPF strengths at the so-called characteristic point. The experimental ratio of the notched FPF strength to the ultimate strength can be only treated as quasi-constant in spite of being not very accurate, as shown in Fig.4. It is logical that the experimental values are inferior to the predicted results for the two laminates. In [7-8], it has been pointed that the predamage at the hole border introduced by specimen fabrication can reduce the stress at the first damage in the laminates. Otherwise, another important cause is that the experimental values are measured just at the hole border but the calculated values are obtained at the characteristic point from which to the hole border it exists a characteristic distance. The stress applied to specimens damaging the hole border may be logically lower than that damaging a place (the characteristic point) far from the hole border due to the stress gradient adjacent to the hole. It can be imaged that the more a characteristic point is near the hole border, the more these two stresses are approaching to each other. In fact, the difference between the calculated and experimental notched FPF strengths in T300/914-1 is larger than that in T300/914-2 partially because the first has a greater characteristic dimension (1.93 mm) than the latter (0.78 mm).

The ultimate strengths (P_u) in Figs.5a and 5b are obtained with equation (4a). In [9], it has been pointed that equation (4a) (the minimal strength model) is more precise than equation (3a) (the point strength model). The predicted results are of a good precision.

It must be noted that the predicted results are not purely numeric because we need to determine the characteristic dimensions with the help of some experimental information. In the present paper, the unnotched strength and the notched strength for the specimens with a diameter of 8 mm were used to determine them. The two laminates have the same geometrical and laminated configurations except the stacking sequences. The unnotched ultimate strengths of the two laminates calculated by means of the classical lamination theory may not be different because the difference originating from stacking sequences are not taken into account.

CONCLUSIONS

The point strength and minimal strength models proposed by Tan may be based on the stress distribution assumption around the hole proposed in the present paper. The characteristic dimension can be considered as the distance between the hole border and the so-called characteristic point at which the ratio of the notched FPF stress or the notched minimal FPF stress to the notched ultimate strength is equal to the ratio of the unnotched FPF strength to the unnotched ultimate strength, and also equal to a material constant. The notched FPF strengths measured by AE techniques and verified by radiography are only the values just at the hole border, but the notched FPF strengths predicted by the two models proposed by Tan are those at the characteristic point. Therefore, the experimental ratio of the notched FPF strengths to the notched ultimate strengths, considered only as quasi-constant, is logically inferior to the ratio predicted by the models. The ultimate strengths predicted by the models are in a good agreement with the experimental values. However, the stress distribution assumption around the hole need still to be proven and how to predict the notched strengths of composite laminates without adopting empirical parameters such as characteristic dimensions is still a problem to be solved.

The principal damage types in T300/914-1 can be described as follows: Cracks initialized adjacent to the hole in the 90° plies evolve towards both to the straight border and to the specimen length direction; The $\pm 45^\circ$ plies are cracked both from the hole border and from the cracks in the 90° plies; Near to the hole border, cracks in the 0° plies can be observed; Evident delamination adjacent to the free-edges can be also clearly observed. The final fractures in every ply are influenced by each other, especially by those in the 90° plies. In T300/914-2, the principal damages are cracks in the 90° plies but they are not evident; The damages in other plies can not be evidently observed and any delamination adjacent to the free-edges can not be seen; The final fractures of every ply are concentrated in the 90° direction. This means that in notched laminates the stacking sequences influence not only the delamination adjacent to the free-edges but also the crack evolution in plies.

REFERENCES

- [1] J.M.Whitney and R.J.Nuismer (1974): Stress fracture criteria for laminated composite containing stress concentration, *J. Composite Materials*, vol.8, 253-256
- [2] R.B.Pipes et al (1979): Notched strength of composite materials, *J. Composite Materials*, vol.13, 148-160
- [3] S.C.Tan (1987): Laminated composites containing an elliptical opening. I. Approximate stress analyses and fracture models, *J. Composite Materials*, vol.21, 925-948
- [4] S.C.Tan (1987): Laminated composites containing an elliptical opening. II. Experiment and model modification, *J. Composite Materials*, vol.21, 949-968
- [5] S.C.Tan (1987): Fracture strength of composite laminates with an elliptical opening, *Composites Science and Technology*, 29, 133-152
- [6] S.C.Tan (1987): Notched strength predication and design laminated composites under in-plane loadings, *J. Composite Materials*, vol.21, 750-780
- [7] Jiayu Xiao (1989): Etude de la résistance à la rupture et du mécanisme de l'endommagement des plaques composites stratifiées contenant un trou soumis à une traction monotone, *Mémoire de D. É. A.*, Université de Technologie de Compiègne, France
- [8] Jiayu Xiao, Dawei Lai and Claude Bathias (1991): Notched strength and damage mechanism of laminated composites with circular holes, *Mechanical Identification of Composites*, Edited by A.Vautrin et al, Elsevier Applied Science, London, 378-385
- [9] Jiayu Xiao (1992): Etude de la prevision de la résistance à la rupture et des mécanismes d'endommagement en traction monotone et cyclique des stratifiés composites non tissés et tissés contenant des trous circulaires, *Doctoral Thesis*, Department of Industrial Materials, CNAM, Paris, France
- [10] Lekhnitskii, S.G. (1986): Anisotropic Plate, Translated from the second Russian edition by Tsai, S.W. and Cheron, Gordon and Breach
- [11] Jiayu Xiao and Claude Bathias: Fatigue behavior of unnotched and notched woven Glass / Epoxy Laminates, to be published in *Composites Science and Technology*